

TEACHER'S PREPARATION FOR TRAINING TRAINING AND TYPES OF TRAINING TRAINING

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Annotation:

the structure of the training session, the elements of the training session, the type of training session, the type of the training session, the teaching methodology, the stages of preparation for the training session and the types of training are mentioned.

Keywords: educational process, lesson, structure of training , training elements, type of training, stages of preparation, types of training.

Introduction

Teacher training is one of the main aspects of successful work in the field of education. Every experienced writer with in-depth knowledge of the field knows the importance of professional training, which allows the teacher not only to teach effectively, but also to overcome various difficulties that arise in the teaching process. One of the main areas of teacher training is acquiring theoretical knowledge about teaching. A professional writer understands that the basis of any educational process is a thorough knowledge of educational psychology, pedagogical approaches and methods, as well as mastery of modern technologies and teaching tools. A teacher must be able to learn the needs of his students and adapt the educational process to their individual characteristics.

However, the teacher's practical training is no less. A writer with extensive experience in this field knows the need for practice, practice, and supervision by experienced teachers. Interaction with other professionals allows the teacher to gain unique experience by observing different styles

and approaches. In addition, the organization of master classes and trainings becomes an integral part of the teacher's training.

An important aspect of teacher training is also its personal development. He must constantly develop, improve his skills, be open to new ideas and approaches. A professional writing teacher knows that patience, empathy, creative thinking, communication skills, and motivating students are essential to success. The teaching profession requires the teacher to be ready for continuous development and self-education.

The preparation of a teacher for an educational session is a unique complex process, in which the quality of any educational session is largely determined by the teacher's good preparation for it. This can be presented as a drawing.

Teacher's preparation for training

The first step.	Learning curriculum. The pedagogue performs this work during the period of preparation for the new academic year. In this, special attention is paid to the main goals and tasks of science. In order to correctly formulate the goals and tasks of the subject, the pedagogue again refers to the teacher in preparation for the study of the next subject by the students. By studying the content of the subject, the pedagogue determines its logical connection with the previously studied material and the material to be studied now. The correct formulation of the goal of this activity allows to determine the place of each training session in the system of training sessions on the studied topic.
The second step.	Acquaintance with methodological literature and their study. By studying the content of the next subject in the textbook, the pedagogue examines the available sections of the textbook, school recommendations, familiarizes himself with articles in magazines, collects the necessary materials for the general study plan of the subjects.
The third step.	The textbook material is studied on the specific topic of the training session. During the study of this material, the pedagogue will consider the logic and validity of its presentation in terms of the development of the students and the level of preparation. The main focus is to focus on the implementation of the principle of presentation of the educational material in the training session. The course of the training session, the method of conducting it are carefully thought out.
The fourth step.	Preparation and study of teaching materials necessary for this training session. The pedagogue not only familiarizes himself with the existing manuals, but also examines the e-learning sites and listens to the audio manuals. Additional attention is paid to the preparation of educational demonstrations and laboratory work. The pedagogue will carefully consider the technique of conducting it.
Fifth step.	Development of a training plan. The lesson planner is the final results of the teacher's preparation for the lesson. It is created taking into account the real progress in the study of the subject in the calendar-thematic planning acoc.

In order to carry out the design of educational activities in the development of the plan of the training session, it is necessary to take into account the level of preparation of the learners for the conscious mastering of the learning material, in addition, to consider the difficulties encountered by the learners, to think of ways to overcome them (for example, individual work). The lesson plan should be large and contain a lot of information. Its shape and size should be convenient for the work of the pedagogue.

At the stage of preparation for training, it is necessary to pay attention to the following: carefully read the contents of the doctor's sections in preparation for the training; study the content of this section; analysis of educational material; forming the goal of training, answering questions about what you want to achieve as a result of training; to think about what to focus the activity of learners on solving educational training problems; choose the necessary methodological tools that are most convenient for this training session and group; use the weapons selected according to your capabilities, determine your impact during the training session; think about the structure of the training session, its course; specify all this in the plan or the concept of the training session; repeat the emergency situations of the plan yourself.

Training sessions. The course of the training: it determines the main stages of the training, their sequence (from the beginning to the end), the time allocated to each stage, the content of each stage, the forms of work of the learner and the pedagogue: organizational level: recognition, working with the magazine, announcing the topic of the training ; preparation: practice, etc.; acociy qicm: theory, practice, transfer forms and methods; final stage: finalize training and form and style. The process of concluding the training consists of two parts: 1) the pedagogue concludes the training together with the students. Answers the questions: What did he know? What did he learn? In other words, was the training goal achieved?; 2) the evaluation procedure of students during the educational process determines their personal achievements. The form of the conclusion of the educational session is determined independently by the pedagogue. The session ends with the announcement of the topic of the next session. At the end of the lesson, the pedagogue analyzes the lesson by himself based on the evaluation criteria.

Literature, didactic materials and technical resources used in preparation for training. The lesson includes the following important elements (steps): checking the completion of previous work, presentation of a new topic, practice under the guidance of a teacher, other independent practice of learners, self-monitoring and evaluation of work results, conclusion of the lesson, determination of homework, necessary repetition, control of learners' knowledge.

The first step: checking the completion of previous works. The main task is to establish a relationship between the pedagogue and the learner, to ensure the readiness of learners for further work, to involve them in productive teaching activities.

The complexity of the teacher's work is that the process of processing new information by students is determined by what he knows and knows about this problem. Therefore, in this regard, the pedagogue should solve the following questions: How should the teacher and the students respond to the information and get to work? To what extent was the formation of internal readiness to learn new materials achieved, what is the general level of motivation of the group, and is it possible to start learning new materials now? In this case, the pedagogue's main actions are as follows: helping learners to get started: choosing a number of questions to repeat; in order to determine the level of general acquired knowledge, to organize a live dialogue of learners; creating problem situations before learning new material.

We see that the beginning of the training is associated with co'orash in its traditional understanding. It is in repetition that learners have a lively dialogue, in which they speak freely, express their views, and discuss. They are not afraid to hear unsatisfying opinions, to face difficult situations.

The teacher supports, directs, corrects, completes, but does not evaluate the conversation during the dialogue. He has the right to use three types of feedback when working with learners: praise the learner, guide, clarify, and repeat misunderstood material.

As long as the pedagogue has no right to any negative discussion, learners do not expect disappointment or reprimands from the pedagogue. They can make mistakes. In such groups, learners are interested in learning more about what the teacher has to offer, and during repetition they require additional knowledge from the teacher. In this part of the work, it is necessary to abandon the superficial evaluation and assessment of the learner's abilities and interests in the

educational process. The most important is the effective use of the active involvement of all learners in cognitive activities at the beginning of the training session.

Second step: to present the new topic. The teacher's monologue is important at the introduction of a new topic. Without his help, it is impossible to master the content of the educational material, to introduce them to additional information, to arouse motivation for independent cognitive activities. In this work, the action of the pedagogue includes the following: allocation of information that serves as a basis for learning the topics; to systematize this material, to organize it in the appropriate form so that the learner can understand it; search for tips that allow to activate the thoughts of learners in the process of mastering new material; striving for its accuracy and simple description in the delivery of information; preparation to help those who need help explaining.

The third step: practice under the guidance of a teacher. This is done in order to timely correct errors in the learner's understanding of new material and provide feedback. In this case, the action of the pedagogue: gives prompts and invites students to respond to him (raise hands, individual answers, short written works, etc.); stops to correct mistakes or repeats material if learners do not understand something, tends to avoid misunderstandings and ambiguities; determines whether there is a need for written work that demonstrates a proper understanding of the material.

The fourth step: independent practice of learners, independent of others. It is a group discussion on the problem to be studied, it is an emac between the learner and the pedagogue, but also between the learners on the learned material. The teacher is given the role of cpiker, organizer of mutual exchange of ideas. He should know how to organize the interaction of students and how to conduct a discussion. In the organization of independent practice, the pedagogue has the right to perform the following functions: to give questions, to transfer them from one student to another, to conclude the learning results in order to highlight the important questions of the subject.

The main goal of the teacher is to attract more students to the discussion, to help them to act independently in the formation of conclusions. This part of the training session is similar to a traditional lecture, the teacher asks questions, listens to the answers of the learners, makes clarifications, etc. The merit of independent practice. It consists of independent disclosure of the content of the studied subject.

Group dickuccia, the most powerful instrument of knowledge, is questioned. Regardless of how it goes, the pedagogue will see the degree of mastering of the studied material, the misunderstandings that have arisen. The same observations allow for clear guidance in the content of subsequent training. Pedagogical actions: keeping dickuccia within the subject; using different tips to attract more learners to dickuccia.

Fifth step: mutual control of work results and self-evaluation. The first task is to avoid coercion. Monitoring and evaluation should be holistic. Sixth step: end of training session. It should be closely related to maqqad. Seventh step: information about the housekeeper. It has creativity and practical capabilities.

Control of knowledge acquisition by learners. During the training session, the control functions are carried out by the administration and pedagogics for individual students, for all groups. They bring out the degree of successful progress of learners in learning new material, and also shed light on the problems and difficulties that arise in the process of educating them. With the help of Tects: an important control check is carried out at the end of the quarter, half-year, annual academic year.

Evaluation criteria of educational training: creation and support of learning interest and activity of students, proper use of training time, use of various methods and methods of teaching, practical importance of acquired knowledge and skills, level of interpersonal relationship between pedagogue and student. The rating is done on the following scale: pact-0, average-1, high-2. These

criteria are used in the analysis by the pedagogue himself, as well as in the analysis of the training by the administration and the team of the pedagogue.

Compilation of the basic tasks of the training. An interest in creative activities lies in additional education. This is done by free choice based on the individual capabilities of the person. It is necessary to think about how to organize the training session to give the learner additional knowledge and to teach them to apply it in practice.

The training together determines the following signs: educational, educational and developmental goals, selection of specific educational material and the level of its mastery in accordance with the goals, achievement of the goals by choosing the most suitable methods and methods of teaching.

There are different approaches to choosing the necessary structural elements of training. The general didactic structure of the training is characterized by the following components: actualization of previous knowledge and means of action, formation of new knowledge and means of action, formation of application skills.

In the practice of additional education, the following important steps of training are highlighted: setting the goal, repeating what has been learned, explaining new material, consolidating what has been learned, summarizing and systematizing new knowledge, monitoring the knowledge and skills of learners. Knowledge of the capabilities of each child, mastering the methodology of their organization, additional education allows the pedagogue to construct training according to different structures and tasks.

Types of training

Familiarization with new material.	In the exercise of acquiring new knowledge, tasks are set on understanding, thinking, and defining concepts. Theoretical material is mastered by training: informing about the topic, goal, training tasks and the motivator of educational activities, preparing to learn new material by repeating basic concepts, familiarizing with new material, pre-understanding and consolidating new material in practice, ending the training.
what has been learned .	Its main didactic purpose is the formation of specific skills: awareness of the topic, purpose and tasks of training, motivation for teaching, application of it in practical activities and repetition of what has been learned, prior acquisition of knowledge in new and changed conditions for the purpose of skill formation and revision of what has been learned, ending the training.
Training to apply knowledge and skills.	In the process of applying knowledge and skills, the following stages are distinguished: repetition and correction of important knowledge and skills, analysis of tasks and methods of their implementation, preparation of necessary equipment, independent performance of practical tasks, control and self-control during the performance of tasks. This is connected with the structure of the training of applying knowledge and skills: informing about the topic, the purpose and tasks of the training, the sequence of applying practical actions in the performance of the specified tasks and repeating the content, additional education by the pedagogue to control the students' independent performance of practical tasks, summarizing the results of the completed tasks and systematization, end of training.
Generalization and	It cannot be concluded that the process of mastering the educational material by the learner has been completed. This process implies a

systematization of knowledge.	sequence of actions such as: understanding, thinking, generalization of acquired knowledge, formation of knowledge and skills, assimilation of complex knowledge, practical activities. The following structural elements are highlighted: setting training goals, repeating and correcting basic knowledge, summarizing and systematizing concepts, the acquired knowledge system, applying them to practical tasks, mastering concepts necessary to perform practical tasks, drawing conclusions.
Knowledge and skills review and editing exercise.	Control and correction of knowledge and skills is carried out in each training session. After studying one or several topics, the pedagogue carries out the necessary control and correction work in order to determine the level of knowledge acquisition of students. Acocida of this takes concrete solutions to improve the educational process. Structure: setting training goals and tasks, conducting an instruction, checking the learner's knowledge of theoretical material, checking the learner's skills of independent application of knowledge in practice, making a conclusion.

The types of training that can be used in teacher training range from formal education and courses to self-study through specialist literature, online courses or learning from the best practices of other teachers. A combined approach that includes theoretical and practical training leads to the most effective result.

Therefore, a professional writer with extensive experience in the field of education knows that the preparation of the teacher plays a key role in achieving quality results in the educational process. A teacher with theoretical knowledge, practical experience, and personal qualities can effectively teach students to help them develop and achieve their goals, taking into account the individual characteristics of students.

REFERENCES USED

1. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Decree PF-5847-con of October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030". (National database of legal documents, 09.10.2019, 06/19/5847/3887-con; 04.30.2020, 06/20/5987/0521-con).
2. Anorkulova G.M. Factors affecting the organization of the educational process in higher education // "Scientific-collegiate methods of ensuring the quality of training, retraining and upgrading of pedagogic personnel for the system of higher education" materials of the republican scientific-practical conference. - T., -2006. - B. 14-16.
3. Akhmedova M.T. "Technologist of organization of educational training in higher education (in the direction of sewing production preparation)". Dicc... ped.science. candidate. -T.: - 2011, - 128 p.
4. Baikova JI. A., Grebenkina L.K. Pedagogicheskoe macterctvo i pedagogicheckie tehnologii. M., -2000.
5. Bashmakov M.I., Pozdnyakov C.N., Reznik N.A. Planirovanie uchitelem svoey deyatelnocti // Shkolnye tehnologii. -2001. No. 1. C. 133-140.
6. Bershadckiy M.E., Guzeev V.V. Didakticheskie i pcixologicheckie ocnovaniya obrazovatelnoy tehnologii. -M.: Center "Technological Poick", -2003. - 256 c.
7. Begimkulov U.Sh. Theoretical practice of organization and management of informatization of pedagogical educational processes: thesis written for the degree of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences. - Tashkent. -2007. -38 p.
8. Becpalko V.P. Pedagogy and progressive technology education. - M.: Izd-vo Inctituta profeccionalnogo obrazovaniya Minicterctva obrazovaniya Roccii, -1995.

9. Ernazarov A.E. Stages, forms, components and criteria of training of pedagogues in higher education institutions // Sohibgiron star. Socio-research, scientific and popular magazine. – Karshi, 2022. No. 1. 188–193 p . (13.00.01; No. 36).
11. Ernazarov A.E. Modern technologies of organizing educational activities // Innovations in pedagogy and psychology. - Tashkent, 2021. #5. 204-206 p . _ (13.00.01; No. 15).
12. Ernazarov A.E. Improving the effectiveness of educational activities based on problem-based learning technologies // Education, science and innovation. - Tashkent , 2016 . No. 1 . 8 6–89 p . (13.00.01; No. 18).
13. Ernazarov A.E. Innovative technologies and their practical application in the continuous education system. Urganch State University. Journal of scientific research. – Urganch, 2021. #8 . 89–91 p . (13.00.01; No. 31).
14. Ernazarov AE . Methods of modern organization and implementation of training. Journal of innovative publications NX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal ISSN No: 2581 – 4230 VOLUME 6, ISSUE 5, May -2020 . Pages: 311-315.
15. Ernazarov AE . [Specific features of training](https://doi.org/10.31149/ijie.v3i5.375) . International Journal on Integrated Education. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31149/ijie.v3i5.375>. Volume 3, Issue V, May 2020. pp. 30-34.
16. Ernazarov AE . [Clarification of the purpose and design of the training sessions](#) . World Scientific News, Scientific Publishing House "DARWIN". WSN 80 (2017) 101-115 .
17. Ernazarov AE . Features of defining goals and objectives in training. Society and innovations - Obshchestvo i innovatsii - Society and innovations. <https://inscience.uz/index.php/socinov/index>. 15 April 2021 . 444-448.